

Predicting late dropout from nursing education or early dropout from the profession.

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To identify predictors of late academic or early career dropout, and derive a simple model for identifying nursing students and novice nurses with significant increased dropout risk.

Background: Dropout from nursing school and the nursing profession is of great concern for students, educators, as well as graduated nurses. Nurse shortages are a major problem in healthcare worldwide (Drennan & Ross, 2019). Retention of nursing students and novice nurses can contribute to reducing the deficits (Smith-Wacholz et al., 2019). Little is known about the predictors of dropout among nursing students in the later years of their degree programme (late dropout) and early nurse dropout from the profession.

Design: Prospective cohort study with three years of follow-up, among 406 third-year nursing students of the Bachelor of Nursing programme of Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences.

Methods: Data were collected between May 2016 and February 2019 using a self-administered questionnaire. Backward binary multiple logistic regression analyses were used to build a prediction model for dropout.

Results: Dropout from nursing education and at the start of the nursing career totalled 12%. Twelve factors, including male sex (OR 3.76, 95% CI 1.41–10.04), age (OR 1.06, 95% CI 1.00–1.12), migration background (OR 2.42, 95% CI 1.10–5.32), clinical placement setting (including mental healthcare; OR 0.18, 95% CI 0.04–0.83), musculoskeletal symptoms (OR 1.20, 95% CI 1.02–1.42) and psychosocial work characteristics (including exposure to violence; OR 3.13, 95% CI 1.25–7.81) were statistically significant predictors in our dropout model. The explained variance of the final model was 26%.

Conclusion: The study highlights the importance of taking musculoskeletal and mental health symptoms, psychosocial work characteristics, as well as sex, age and migration background into consideration as predictors for dropout among nursing students and novice nurses. This study is a first step towards a predictive model that helps identifying high-risk groups.

Video to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sctalk.2022.100106>.

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Figures and tables

Table 1
Participants' baseline characteristics.

	N (%)	Mean (SD) (range)
Sample size, N	406	
Sex (% female)	363 (89.4%)	
Age (years)		23.7 (5.8) (19–54)
Body Mass Index (BMI) (kg/m ²)		23.4 (3.6) (15.6–41.1)
Height (cm)		170.9 (8.0) (151–199)
Living situation (% with parents)	215 (53.0%)	
Migration background (% Dutch or western migration background)	314 (77.3%)	
Country of birth (% the Netherlands)	365 (89.9%)	
Highest educational level		
• Senior general secondary education	230 (56.7%)	
• Pre-university education & academic higher education	67 (16.5%)	
• Intermediate vocational education and training & in-service training & other	109 (26.8%)	
Educational routing		
• fulltime programme	439 (61.7%)	
• work-study programme	212 (29.8%)	
• part-time study programme	60 (8.4%)	
Current clinical placement		
• hospital	210 (51.7%)	
• elderly care	50 (12.3%)	
• home care	83 (20.4%)	
• mental healthcare	37 (9.1%)	
• other	26 (6.4%)	
<i>Physical work characteristics</i>		
Lifting and bending		40.6 (28.1) (0–150)
Physical job demands		13.1 (3.1) (5–20)
Total time spent working at a screen		3.4 (2.5) (1–24)
Working at a screen (% always-often)	300 (73.9%)	
Nr of colleagues (% 2-more)	199 (49%)	
Nr of patients		7.7 (6.4) (1–80)
<i>Psychosocial work characteristics</i>		
Decision latitude		70.7 (9.8) (38–94)
Psychological job demands		54.1 (4.4) (40–64)
Supervisor support		11.7 (2.6) (4–16)
Co-worker support		12.3 (1.9) (6–16)
<i>Mental health symptoms</i>		
Distress (% no/moderate distress)	237 (58.4%)	
Need for recovery		6.8 (3.1) (0–11)
<i>Physical health symptoms</i>		
Physical activity level (SQUASH)		7.6 (5.3) (0–27)
Any musculoskeletal symptoms at any body part (% regular /long-lasting)	350 (86.2%)	
Symptoms of the upper extremities (CANS) (% regular /long-lasting)	216 (53.2%)	
Low back pain (% regular /long-lasting)	210 (51.7%)	
Symptoms of lower extremities (% regular /long-lasting)	154 (37.9%)	
<i>Proxies of late dropout from nursing education</i>		
Sickness absence (% yes)	116 (28.6%)	
Work engagement		4.4 (1.2) (1–7)
Considering quitting nursing education (% any consideration to quit)	151 (37.2%)	

Table 2
Final model with all significant ($p < 0.1$) predictors for dropout.

Characteristics at baseline	OR [†]	90% CI [‡]	R ^{2§}
Male sex (reference: female)	3.758	1.648–8.569	0.264
Age (per year increase)	1.059	1.008–1.113	
Clinical placement in elderly care (reference: hospital care)	0.272	0.101–0.734	
Clinical placement in home care (reference: hospital care)	0.363	0.148–0.889	

Table 2 (continued)

Characteristics at baseline	OR [†]	90% CI [‡]	R ^{2§}
Clinical placement in mental healthcare (reference: hospital care)	0.179	0.049–0.651	
Migration background (reference: no migration background)	2.419	1.249–4.683	
Never or sometimes working at a screen (reference: often or always working at a screen)	2.925	1.479–5.785	
Exposure to violence (reference: no exposure to violence)	3.125	1.450–6.739	
Exposure to gossip or slander (reference: no exposure to gossip or slander)	1.885	1.015–3.501	
Regular or long term musculoskeletal symptoms (reference: no or occasional musculoskeletal symptoms)	1.201	1.047–1.379	
Work engagement (per unit increase; potential range 0–6)	0.579	0.430–0.781	
Need for recovery (per unit increase; potential range 0–100)	0.830	0.737–0.934	

[†]Odds ratio; [‡]Confidence interval; [§]Explained variance by Nagelkerke R-square test.

Appendix 1

List of potential predictors included in the analysis.

Sociodemographic characteristics	Measurement level, instrument and source
Sex	One single question: ‘What is your sex?; male or female
Age	One single question: ‘What is your age?’
BMI	Calculated from the student’s self-reported height (in centimeters) and weight (in kilograms); BMI = weight/height ²
Living situation	One single question: ‘What is your living situation?’
Migration background	Classification based on Three questions: ‘Where are you born?’, ‘In which country was your mother born?’, ‘In which country was your father born?’; students with a migration background were born in another country, or had at least one parent who was born in another country.
First language	One single question: ‘Is Dutch your first language?; yes or no
Highest educational level	One single question: ‘What is your highest (completed) education?’
Educational routing	One single question: ‘Which educational route are you following?’; Fulltime, Dual or Parttime
Current clinical placement	One single question: ‘In which health care sector are you currently doing your clinical placement or are you working?’
Physical work characteristics	
Lifting and bending	Lifting and bending scale, NEXT Study-Group [1]
Physical job demands	Job Content Questionnaire (JCQ), [2]
Working at a screen	Dutch Questionnaire on the Experience and Evaluation of Work (VBBA), [3]
Total time spent working at a screen	
Number of colleagues on-site	One single question: ‘How many colleagues do you work with in a day during your clinical placement/work?’
Number of patients	One single question: ‘How many patients do you care for on average on a weekday during a day shift?’
Help from care provider for physical symptoms	One single question: ‘Have you sought help from a health care provider for physical complaints in the current clinical placement/work period?’
Physical health symptoms	
Any musculoskeletal symptoms at any body part	Dutch Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (DMQ) [4]
Symptoms of the upper extremities (CANS)	
Low back pain	
Symptoms of the lower extremities	
Psychosocial work characteristics	
Sickness Absenteeism due to work stress	Sickness Absenteeism, NEA, [5]
Sickness Absenteeism due to work stress for >4 weeks	
Malfunctioning due to work stress	Dutch Questionnaire on the Experience and Evaluation of Work (VBBA), [3]
Malfunctioning due to work stress for >4 weeks	
Loss of work pleasure due to work stress	
Seriously considered changing clinical placement/education	
Help from care provider for social problems	
Bullying	COPSOQ II, [6]
Violence	
Gossip or slander	
Decision latitude	Job Content Questionnaire (JCQ), [2]
Psychological job demands	
Supervisor social support	
Co-worker social support	
Coping; expression of emotions	Utrechtse Coping Lijst UCL, [7]
Coping; active handling	
Coping; Palliative reaction	
Coping; Social support	
Work family conflict (WFC)	WFC scale and FWC scale, [8]
Family work conflict (FWC)	
Occupational self-efficacy	Occupational Self-Efficacy Scale short version, [9]
Mental health symptoms	
Distress	Distress Screener, [10]
Need for recovery (NFR)	NFR scale, [11]
Other determinants	
Physical activity level	Short QUESTIONNAIRE to ASSES Health enhancing physical activity (SQUASH), [12]
Work engagement	Utrechtse Bevoegenheidschaal (UBES-S), [13]
Sick leave during academic year	One single question: ‘Have you ever been absent this academic year?; yes / no
Not absent, but sick	One single question: ‘Did it happen in the current clinical placement/work period that you started an placement/work while you knew that you should have reported sick?; No / yes, sometimes / yes, regularly
Considering quitting nursing education	One single question: ‘I am considering quitting my studies.’; 10 point likert scale: by no means (1).....(10) certainly

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jos H.A.M. Kox: Conceptualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Joost S. van der Zwan:** Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Johanna H. Groenewoud:** Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Jos Runhaar:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Sita M.A. Bierma-Zeinstra:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Ellen J.M. Bakker:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Harald S. Miedema:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Allard J. van der Beek:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Cécile R.L. Boot:** Conceptualization, Validation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Pepijn D.D.M. Roelofs:** Conceptualization, Validation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Further reading

Scientific output from the SPRiNG study

- [1] E.J. Bakker, J.H. Kox, H.S. Miedema, S. Bierma-Zeinstra, J. Runhaar, C.R. Boot, ... P.D. Roelofs, Physical and mental determinants of dropout and retention among nursing students: protocol of the SPRiNG cohort study, *BMC Nurs.* 17 (1) (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-018-0296-9>.
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Joost van der Zwan studied and worked at Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences since 2005, where he started as a researcher at Research Centre Innovations in Care. Within the research project SPRiNG Starting Strong in Nursing, he contributed to the analyses of the research on the prediction model. He also assisted PhD students with their research projects. Among other things, he was involved in performing literature updates, analyzing interviews with ATLAS.Ti, analyzing data with SPSS and co-writing scientific articles for publications in scientific journals.

Dr. Harald Miedema is lector of Labor and Health at Research Centre Innovations in Care of Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences since 2005. His lectorate deals with work-related problems or work limitations caused by chronic diseases or conditions. Dr. Miedema is a physician and epidemiologist. He combines his position at Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences with a position as medical advisor of the Netherlands Health Care Institute. In 2016, he received his doctorate for his dissertation "Towards a better approach to non-specific complaints of the postural and locomotor system," on back and arm, neck and shoulder (CANS) complaints and their relationship to work. Currently he is involved in the SPRiNG – Living Lab project.

Dr. Hanny Groenewoud studied Medicine at the University of Utrecht. After several years working as a company doctor, she chose a job as a researcher at the Institute for Social Health Care at Erasmus MC. There she obtained her doctorate in 2002 on a study of euthanasia and other medical end-of-life decisions. Dr. Groenewoud has been working at Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences since 2005, where she started as a researcher at Research Centre Innovations in Care, focusing on the care of elderly people living at home with dementia and their caregivers. Since then she combines her experience as researcher also in education by -among other things- supervising fourth year nursing students in their graduation research. As a researcher, she is involved in the SPRiNG – Living Lab project, where she contributes to analyzing results and writing (scientific) publications.

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Dr. Jos Runhaar is an Assistant Professor at the Department of General Practice of Erasmus MC. He was trained as Human Movement Scientist at the Vrije University Amsterdam. For his PhD, he performed the first ever RCT on the primary prevention of osteoarthritis. The research line of Dr. Runhaar aims to improve the diagnosis and treatment of musculoskeletal disorders by general practitioners and physiotherapists and to shift the treatment of musculoskeletal disorders to the early disease phase. Dr. Runhaar served different scientific committees, including the Research and Training Committee of OARSI (Chair), the Scientific Advisory Board for the Dutch Arthritis Society, the Organizing Committee for the 2020 International Workshop on OA Imaging (co-Chair), the Advisory Board for the International Society of OA Imaging and multiple (inter)national Thesis Assessment Committees.

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